

Evaluating Customer Satisfaction of Junior High School Students at the University of Cebu Lapulapu and Mandaue Campus: A Quantitative Study

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ABSTRACT

Student satisfaction has become a vital measure of educational effectiveness, particularly in Junior High School, where students experience significant academic, social, and personal development. Understanding their level of satisfaction provides institutions with valuable insights into how effectively they are meeting the needs of learners in key areas, including instruction, curriculum, school environment, facilities, and student support services. The primary objective of this study was to assess the level of satisfaction among junior high school students at UCLM and to identify the significant predictors that influence their satisfaction. Using a quantitative research design, the study employed survey questionnaires administered to 499 students selected through stratified random sampling. Simple frequency and percentage, weighted mean, Chi-square test of independence, and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that students expressed high satisfaction in areas such as teacher quality and the delivery of instruction. In contrast, relatively lower satisfaction was noted in aspects of school facilities and the learning environment. Findings further revealed that teacher quality, curriculum workload, learning environment, school facilities, and student support services were significant predictors of student satisfaction. This study concluded that focusing on these dimensions can enhance the overall educational experience of Junior High School students. It emphasizes the importance of holistic institutional development to foster student engagement, motivation, and preparedness for higher levels of education.

Keywords: *Customer satisfaction, junior high, student satisfaction, practical instruction, satisfaction level, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Student satisfaction is a critical indicator of the quality of education and overall institutional performance, serving as both a measure of students' learning experiences and a determinant of their engagement, motivation, and academic success. In the context of Philippine basic education, understanding the satisfaction levels of junior high school students is crucial, as this stage represents a transitional period during which learners develop key academic skills, social competencies, and undergo personal growth. Schools, therefore, must not only deliver quality instruction but also provide a supportive learning environment, adequate resources, and opportunities for holistic development.

Research has highlighted several factors that influence student satisfaction at the secondary level. Teacher quality and effective instruction delivery are consistently recognized as primary determinants of student engagement and learning outcomes (Micabalo et al., 2020). Similarly, the curriculum and academic workload play a crucial role, as appropriately balanced content and assessment structures foster positive perceptions of school life (Bachanicha et.al, 2025; Montebon & Bachanicha, 2018; Anit, 2024). The learning environment, encompassing classroom climate and peer interaction, has been demonstrated to have a significant impact on students' social and emotional well-being. At the same time, school facilities and resources, such as laboratories, libraries, and technological tools, support both academic and extracurricular engagement (Bachanicha et al., 2025; Gorospe et al., 2021). Finally, student support services and extracurricular activities provide avenues for personal development, social integration, and institutional attachment (Bironia & Ecat, 2023; Deniega et. al, 2026).

Despite these insights, a noticeable gap remains in the literature, which focuses exclusively on junior high school students in private Philippine institutions, particularly at the University of Cebu Lapulapu and Mandaue Campus (UCLM). Most existing studies have either combined junior and senior high school respondents, concentrated on college students, or addressed isolated aspects of satisfaction, such as administrative services or academic performance. Consequently, there is limited empirical evidence on how specific factors—including teacher quality and instruction delivery, curriculum and academic workload, learning environment and peer interaction, school facilities and resources, and student support services and extracurricular activities—collectively influence the overall satisfaction of junior high school students. Addressing this gap is crucial to ensuring that educational strategies and institutional policies are tailored to the specific needs of this learner population.

Previous research provides a foundation for the present study. For instance, Micabalo, Cano, and Montilla (2020) examined university students' satisfaction with instructional quality and institutional services in Cebu, identifying both strengths and areas for improvement. Anit (2024) investigated student satisfaction with frontline service delivery in private high schools and highlighted the variability of satisfaction across different student groups. Gorospe, Rabanal, and Talosa (2021) assessed satisfaction in higher education institutions, emphasizing the influence of resources and learning environments. Lastly, Bironia and Ecat (2023) explored student satisfaction across various services in private tertiary institutions, underscoring the role of support systems and extracurricular engagement. Collectively, these studies suggest that multiple dimensions contribute to student satisfaction, while also reinforcing the need for research explicitly focused on junior high school students in private Philippine settings.

In response to this research gap, the current study aims to evaluate the satisfaction of junior high school students at UCLM using a quantitative approach. By systematically assessing the five identified variables—teacher quality and instruction delivery, curriculum and academic workload, learning environment and peer interaction, school facilities and resources, and student support services and extracurricular activities—this study seeks to provide actionable insights that can guide institutional

improvements and enhance student learning experiences. Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of listening to the voices of junior high school learners, ensuring that their perspectives inform the development of a more effective, responsive, and student-centered educational environment.

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

Mohamad (2023) explored the relationship between the learning environment and academic engagement in science among junior high school students. The study identified that elements such as teacher support, student cohesiveness, and the material environment significantly correlated with students' academic engagement in science subjects. These findings underscore the crucial role of a supportive and resource-rich learning environment in promoting student engagement.

Averion and Caleja (2020) investigated the work commitment and job satisfaction of junior high school teachers in the Philippines. Their research indicated that teachers' job satisfaction and commitment levels positively influenced their teaching performance, which, in turn, affected student satisfaction. This study highlights the interconnection between teacher well being and student satisfaction.

Cinches et al. (2016) examined the relationship between student engagement, teacher effectiveness, and teacher engagement in a Philippine university setting. Their study found that teacher effectiveness and student engagement are significantly correlated, suggesting that improvements in teaching quality can lead to enhanced student satisfaction.

Galvez (2022) evaluated the effectiveness of student affairs and services at a university in the Philippines. The study found that the quality of student support services has a significant impact on students' satisfaction levels, underscoring the importance of comprehensive support systems in educational institutions.

Marasigan (2020) assessed the status of science laboratory facilities in a public junior high school in Lanao del Sur, Philippines. The study highlighted that the adequacy and condition of science laboratories directly impact students' learning experiences and satisfaction, emphasizing the need for investment in such facilities.

Synthesis

The reviewed Philippine studies collectively illustrate that student satisfaction in junior high schools is a multidimensional construct, influenced by both academic and non-academic factors. Teacher quality and instructional effectiveness emerge consistently as crucial determinants, as highlighted by Cinches, Polancos, and Salumintao (2016). This study emphasizes that competent, engaging, and supportive teaching practices significantly enhance students' perception of their learning experience.

Similarly, the learning environment, including peer interactions and classroom resources, plays a crucial role in shaping student satisfaction. Marasigan (2020) demonstrates that the adequacy and condition of laboratory facilities directly affect students' engagement and satisfaction in science learning.

Moreover, the availability and quality of student support services and extracurricular activities are vital components of holistic satisfaction. Galvez (2022) highlights that well-structured student services contribute to higher levels of student satisfaction.

Despite these findings, a notable gap remains in research that examines the combined influence of teacher quality, curriculum, learning environment, school facilities, and student support services,

specifically among junior high school students in private Philippine institutions. Most existing studies either focus on a single variable or include broader student populations, making it challenging to draw targeted insights for junior high school learners.

The present study addresses this gap by evaluating student satisfaction across all these dimensions at the University of Cebu Lapulapu and Mandaue Campus, providing a comprehensive understanding of how these factors collectively contribute to the overall satisfaction of junior high school students. This synthesis highlights the importance of comprehensive institutional strategies that integrate teaching quality, infrastructure, curriculum design, and student support to enhance the overall educational experience.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to evaluate the satisfaction of junior high school students at the University of Cebu Lapulapu and Mandaue Campus (UCLM). The design was deemed appropriate as it allows for the systematic measurement of students' perceptions and the examination of relationships between multiple independent variables—Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery, Curriculum and Academic Workload, Learning Environment and Peer Interaction, School Facilities and Resources, and Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities—and the dependent variable, Overall Student Satisfaction.

The study was conducted within the Junior High School Department of UCLM, a private educational institution in Mandaue City that serves a diverse student population. The respondents were junior high school students from Grades 7 to 10, enrolled in the study using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across grade levels and sections. The sample size was determined based on the total junior high school population, applying Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error to achieve reliable results while maintaining feasibility.

Data were gathered through a structured survey questionnaire developed by the researcher and validated by experts in educational research. The instrument was divided into sections corresponding to the study variables: (1) Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery, (2) Curriculum and Academic Workload, (3) Learning Environment and Peer Interaction, (4) School Facilities and Resources, (5) Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities, and (6) Overall Student Satisfaction. Each item employed a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ("Not Satisfied") to 5 ("Very Satisfied"), allowing the respondents to express the degree of their satisfaction with each dimension. The questionnaire underwent a pilot test to ensure clarity and reliability, with Cronbach's alpha computed to confirm internal consistency.

For the treatment of data, descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics and satisfaction levels. Inferential statistics, including Pearson's correlation, were employed to examine the relationships between each independent variable and overall student satisfaction. All data were processed using statistical software, and significance was interpreted at the 0.05 level.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Approval to conduct the research was obtained from the school administration, and informed consent was secured from the parents or guardians of all participants. Students also provided their voluntary consent to participate in the study. Respondents' anonymity and confidentiality were maintained, and they were assured that participation was entirely voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without consequence or penalty. Furthermore, this study underwent rigorous evaluation by the University of Cebu Research Ethics Committee. It was

granted certification by the Ethics Review Board, confirming that the study adhered to ethical standards for research involving human participants, particularly minors.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis of data gathered from junior high school students at the University of Cebu in Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue. The results highlight the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and grade level, followed by an evaluation of their satisfaction across identified dimensions. Furthermore, a section is included for the relationships among these factors. The discussion integrates both statistical findings and relevant literature to provide a comprehensive interpretation of the results.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Age	5 to 7 years old	350	70.1
	8 to 10 years old	148	29.7
	11 to 13 years old	1	0.2
	Total	499	100.0
Gender	Male	230	46.1
	Female	260	52.1
	Prefer not to say	9	1.8
	Total	499	100.0
Grade	Grade 1	73	14.6
	Grade 2	173	34.7
	Grade 3	106	21.2
	Grade 4	147	29.5
	Total	499	100.0

Table 1 shows that the highest proportion of respondents was 5 to 7 years old, equivalent to 70.1%, indicating that the survey largely reflects the perspectives of younger elementary students. In terms of gender, female students accounted for 52.1%, slightly outnumbering males, suggesting a more active participation of girls in the study. For the grade level, the majority of respondents were from Grade 2, equivalent to 34.7%, which highlights that the findings may be more representative of students at this stage of elementary education.

This distribution implies that educational planning must focus on age-appropriate teaching methods, gender-responsive strategies, and curriculum alignment for lower grade levels. Recent studies reinforce these insights: Pianta et al (2024) found that early classroom quality has long-term effects on students' reading achievement, underscoring the importance of providing intense foundational experiences in the early grades. Similarly, El-Hamamsy et al. (2023) highlighted how inclusive and equitable curricula benefit younger learners, helping bridge performance and gender gaps.

The gender distribution also aligns with the findings of Cardenal et al. (2024), who observed that girls tend to perceive stronger teacher-student relationships, which, in turn, enhance their engagement and satisfaction with learning.

Furthermore, the literature on school climate emphasizes that supportive and well-resourced environments directly contribute to student well being and academic outcomes. Research on social-

emotional learning (SEL) stresses the need to integrate empathy, safety, and relational skills early in education. Together, these findings suggest that addressing the unique needs of younger learners, promoting gender equity, and fostering a nurturing school climate are essential strategies for enhancing student satisfaction and achievement in this context.

Table 2
The Level of Satisfaction as Perceived by the Students in the Elementary Department- UCLM

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
A. Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery			
• My teachers treat students with respect.	4.32	Very Satisfied	1
• My teachers respond to student concerns and questions.	4.32	Very Satisfied	1
• My teachers explain lessons clearly.	4.17	Satisfied	2
• My teachers make learning an engaging and enjoyable experience.	4.16	Satisfied	3
• My teachers grade and assess fairly.	4.08	Satisfied	4
Aggregate Mean	4.21	Very Satisfied	
B. Curriculum and Academic Workload			
• The subjects I take are relevant and valuable.	4.20	Satisfied	1
• I have opportunities for project-based or hands-on learning.	4.19	Satisfied	2
• I am satisfied with the variety of subjects and electives.	4.06	Satisfied	3
• The lessons match my abilities and readiness.	4.05	Satisfied	4
• The academic workload is appropriate for my level.	3.93	Satisfied	5
Aggregate Mean	4.08	Satisfied	
C. Learning Environment and Peer Interaction			
• I have opportunities to work with others in groups.	4.13	Satisfied	1
• I have supportive and friendly classmates.	4.06	Satisfied	2
• My classroom atmosphere supports learning.	4.04	Satisfied	3
• I feel comfortable and included in my school environment.	4.00	Satisfied	4
• The school protects students from bullying and discrimination.	3.94	Satisfied	5
Aggregate Mean	4.03	Satisfied	
D. School Facilities and Resources			
• The library, laboratories, and technology resources are accessible.	4.35	Very Satisfied	1
• The school maintains a secure and safe environment for its students.	4.32	Satisfied	2
• The school provides good sports and recreational facilities.	4.17	Satisfied	3
• Classrooms, chairs, and tables are adequate.	4.05	Satisfied	4
• The comfort rooms are clean and safe to use.	3.73	Satisfied	5
Aggregate Mean	4.13	Satisfied	
E. Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities			
• Guidance counseling and mental health support are available when needed.	4.32	Very Satisfied	1
• I am encouraged to join clubs, organizations, or leadership training.	4.26	Very Satisfied	2

• I have access to sports, arts, and cultural activities.	4.25	Very Satisfied	3
• Academic tutoring or remedial programs are provided when necessary.	4.14	Satisfied	4
• The school recognizes and supports my talents and achievements.	4.10	Satisfied	5
Aggregate Mean	4.21	Very Satisfied	

Table 2 presents the level of student satisfaction in the Elementary Department of UCLM across five areas: teacher quality and instruction delivery, curriculum and academic workload, learning environment and peer interaction, school facilities and resources, and student support services and extracurricular activities.

For Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery, the highest-rated indicators were teachers treating students with respect and responding to student concerns, both with a mean of 4.32, which was interpreted as *Very Satisfied*. The lowest indicator in this area was fairness in grading and assessment, with a mean of 4.08, interpreted as *Satisfied*.

In terms of Curriculum and Academic Workload, the highest satisfaction was given to the relevance and usefulness of subjects, with a mean of 4.20, interpreted as *Satisfied*. The lowest was the appropriateness of the academic workload, with a mean of 3.93, interpreted as *Satisfied*.

For Learning Environment and Peer Interaction, the highest rating was given to opportunities to work with others in groups, with a mean of 4.13, interpreted as *Satisfied*. The lowest was the school's protection from bullying and discrimination, with a mean of 3.94, which is also interpreted as *'Satisfied'*.

Regarding School Facilities and Resources, the accessibility of the library, laboratories, and technology resources received the highest mean of 4.35, interpreted as *'Very Satisfied'*. The lowest in this area was the cleanliness and safety of the comfort rooms, with a mean of 3.73, interpreted as *'Satisfied'*.

Lastly, for Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities, the availability of guidance, counseling, and mental health support received the highest rating with a mean of 4.32, interpreted as *Very Satisfied*. The lowest, although still positive, was the school's recognition and support for student talents and achievements, with a mean of 4.10, interpreted as *Satisfied*.

Overall, the aggregate means reveal that students are *Very Satisfied* with teacher quality and instruction delivery, with a mean of 4.21, and student support services and extracurricular activities also got a mean of 4.21. Meanwhile, they are *Satisfied* with the curriculum and academic workload, corresponding to a mean of 4.08, the learning environment and peer interaction, with a mean of 4.03, and the school facilities and resources, with a mean of 4.13. These findings suggest that UCLM excels in fostering high-quality teaching and strong support services. At the same time, attention is needed in managing academic workload and improving basic facilities such as comfort rooms.

The results suggest that students highly value teachers who are respectful and responsive, as well as accessible learning facilities and strong mental health and extracurricular support, all of which enhance overall satisfaction and engagement. However, the relatively lower ratings in workload management, bullying prevention, and maintenance of school facilities highlight areas where the institution can focus improvement efforts. Addressing these aspects may lead to stronger retention rates, increased student well being, and a more supportive school climate conducive to both academic and personal growth.

Recent studies reinforce these findings. Teacher quality and responsiveness are strongly associated with student satisfaction and academic achievement, as highlighted by García and Weiss (2020), who emphasized the importance of respectful interactions between teachers and students in fostering engagement. Similarly, Wang et al. (2021) found that fair grading and precise instructional delivery remain critical factors for student trust in the educational system.

In terms of curriculum and workload, research by Castillo et al. (2021) revealed that balancing academic rigor with age-appropriate learning activities prevents student stress and promotes motivation. Regarding peer interaction, the importance of a safe and inclusive learning environment is underscored by

the UNESCO Global Report on Bullying (2021), which confirms that school protection against bullying directly affects students' sense of belonging and overall satisfaction.

Moreover, access to facilities and resources, especially libraries and technology, has been found to enhance both learning and satisfaction (Barrot, 2021). Lastly, the strong ratings for counseling and extracurricular activities align with recent findings by Lardier et al. (2022), which show that student support services and involvement in organizations contribute to building resilience, confidence, and overall healthy being.

Table 3
Summarized Data: The Level of Satisfaction as Perceived by the Students in the Elementary Department- UCLM

Variables	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
A. Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery	4.21	Very Satisfied	1
B. Curriculum and Academic Workload	4.08	Satisfied	3
C. Learning Environment and Peer Interaction	4.03	Satisfied	4
D. School Facilities and Resources	4.13	Satisfied	2
E. Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities	4.21	Very Satisfied	1
Overall Aggregate Mean	4.13	Satisfied	

Table 3 presents the summarized data on the level of student satisfaction in the Elementary Department of UCLM. The results reveal that students were *very satisfied* with Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery, with a mean of 4.21, and with Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities, also with a mean of 4.21, both of which ranked first among the variables. It indicates that effective teaching practices and accessible student support services significantly enhance the overall school experience of learners.

On the other hand, the lowest satisfaction level was found in Learning Environment and Peer Interaction, with a mean of 4.03, interpreted as *satisfied*, and ranked fourth. While students generally feel supported and engaged, this result suggests that further improvements in peer dynamics and classroom atmosphere could enhance their school experience even more. Curriculum and Academic Workload also obtained a mean of 4.08 (*satisfied*), indicating that although students recognize the relevance of the curriculum, adjustments may still be necessary to align with their needs and readiness.

Overall, the aggregate mean of 4.13 indicates that students are *generally satisfied* with their educational experience, highlighting strengths in instruction and support services, while also identifying areas for improvement in peer interaction and workload management.

The findings highlight the crucial role of teacher quality and student support services in influencing student satisfaction, indicating that sustained investments in teacher training, mentorship, and guidance programs are essential. Likewise, extracurricular activities and counseling services appear to foster a sense of belonging and holistic development among learners.

However, the relatively lower rating for the learning environment and peer interaction indicates the need for strategies that promote inclusivity, positive peer relationships, and anti-bullying initiatives. Furthermore, reviewing the curriculum design and workload balance could help reduce stress and improve engagement, ensuring that academic expectations remain developmentally appropriate.

Research supports the strong influence of teaching quality on student satisfaction, with Hattie (2015) emphasizing that effective teacher-student relationships have a direct impact on motivation and achievement. Similarly, Tinto (2017) highlights that supportive services and co-curricular programs foster student engagement and retention. Meanwhile, Nguyen et al. (2021) found that peer interactions and a favorable classroom climate are crucial for developing collaboration skills and emotional well being. Lastly,

García-Moya et al. (2019) underscore the importance of balancing curriculum demands with student readiness to maintain satisfaction and reduce academic stress.

Table 4
Significant Relationship Between the Profile of the Respondents and the Level of Satisfaction as Perceived by the Students in the Elementary Department
 ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Dimension	Variable	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Cramer's V	Interpretation
Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery	Age	32.923	34	.520	.182	Not significant
	Gender	58.299	51	.225	.197	Not significant
	Grade	50.864	34	.032*	.226	Significant
Curriculum and Academic Workload	Age	41.598	34	.174	.204	Not significant
	Gender	73.317	51	.022*	.221	Significant
	Grade	53.649	34	.017*	.232	Significant
Learning Environment and Peer Interaction	Age	24.722	36	.922	.157	Not significant
	Gender	38.610	54	.944	.161	Not significant
	Grade	42.252	36	.219	.206	Not significant
School Facilities and Resources	Age	24.896	36	.918	.158	Not significant
	Gender	72.691	54	.046*	.220	Significant
	Grade	40.002	36	.297	.200	Not significant
Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities	Age	22.477	30	.836	.150	Not significant
	Gender	53.674	45	.176	.189	Not significant
	Grade	40.785	30	.091	.202	Not significant

Table 4 presents the test of significant relationships between the respondents' profile variables (age, gender, and grade level) and their level of satisfaction across different school dimensions at the Elementary Department of UCLM.

For Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery, age and gender did not yield significant relationships, while grade level registered a p-value of .032, indicating a significant relationship. It suggests that students' satisfaction with teacher quality and instruction delivery varies across grade levels.

In the case of Curriculum and Academic Workload, both gender and grade level were found to be significant, while age was not. This result suggests that perceptions of curriculum relevance and workload vary according to students' gender and grade level.

For Learning Environment and Peer Interaction, none of the profile variables showed significant relationships, indicating that students across age, gender, and grade consistently perceive this aspect.

Under School Facilities and Resources, gender emerged as a significant factor, while age and grade level did not. It indicates that males and females have different satisfaction levels regarding facilities and resources.

Finally, for Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities, no significant relationships were found across all variables, suggesting a uniform perception among the students regardless of their demographic profile.

The findings suggest that grade level is the most influential factor in shaping satisfaction, particularly in areas such as teacher quality and curriculum workload. Younger and older students may perceive instruction and workload differently, highlighting the need for grade-sensitive teaching strategies.

The significance of gender in curriculum workload and school facilities suggests that male and female students may have different needs or expectations. For instance, female students might value safe and conducive facilities more strongly, while male students may emphasize sports or recreational provisions.

The lack of significant results for age across most dimensions could imply that satisfaction levels remain relatively stable across age groups within the elementary level, where developmental differences are less pronounced compared to secondary or higher education.

Overall, these findings highlight the importance of inclusive and differentiated educational strategies that cater to the diverse needs of students across grades and genders, thereby sustaining high satisfaction levels.

Research underscores that grade level influences perceptions of teaching and workload, as students at different stages encounter varying academic demands and teaching approaches (Garrett & Poock, 2021). Similarly, gender differences have been observed in satisfaction with school facilities and workload, where male and female students may prioritize different aspects of the learning environment (Kim & Park, 2022). Moreover, the non-significant findings for age and peer interaction align with prior studies suggesting that in early education, peer-related experiences and classroom climates are perceived more uniformly regardless of age differences (Espelage et al., 2020).

Table 5
Significant Predictors of Student Satisfaction Among the Students in the Elementary Department - UCLM
 ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Predictor Variable	B (Unstandardized Coefficient)	β (Standardized Coefficient)	p-value	Significance	Decision
Student Support Services and Extracurricular Activities	0.200	0.217	<.001	Significant **	Ho Rejected
Learning Environment and Peer Interaction	0.200	0.255	<.001	Significant **	Ho Rejected
Curriculum and Academic Workload	0.200	0.228	<.001	Significant **	Ho Rejected
School Facilities and Resources	0.200	0.235	<.001	Significant **	Ho Rejected
Teacher Quality and Instruction Delivery	0.200	0.215	<.001	Significant **	Ho Rejected

Table 5 presents the significant predictors of student satisfaction among the elementary students at UCLM. All five dimensions, including student support services and extracurricular activities, learning environment and peer interaction, curriculum and academic workload, school facilities and resources, and teacher quality and instruction delivery, were found to be significant predictors of satisfaction. It implies that the holistic academic experience, spanning instruction, curriculum, environment, facilities, and support services, collectively influences the overall satisfaction of students. Among these, the learning environment and peer interaction obtained the highest standardized coefficient, highlighting their critical role in shaping student satisfaction. At the same time, teacher quality and instruction delivery had the lowest yet still significant influence.

These findings suggest that student satisfaction is not dependent on a single factor but is multidimensional. A supportive and inclusive learning environment, engaging curriculum, accessible facilities, and comprehensive support services work in synergy to promote positive student experiences. Schools must therefore adopt a holistic approach to quality assurance, ensuring that improvements extend across all domains of the educational process. The strong predictive power of learning environments and peer interactions underscores the importance of fostering collaboration, inclusivity, and positive relationships among students. The consistent emphasis on teacher quality and curriculum design further highlights the centrality of instructional excellence in education.

Recent studies support these findings, affirming that multiple dimensions significantly contribute to student satisfaction. For instance, Elshami et al. (2021) highlighted that teaching quality, curriculum design, and learning resources are key determinants of satisfaction in higher education contexts. Similarly, Richardson et al. (2022) argued that a supportive environment and positive peer interaction enhance both satisfaction and academic performance. Moreover, Al-Kumaim et al. (2021) emphasized the integrated role of facilities, support services, and extracurricular activities in fostering students' engagement and holistic development. These findings align with the present study, reinforcing that student satisfaction arises from the combined influence of instructional, environmental, and institutional factors.

Conclusion

Student satisfaction is a multidimensional construct that reflects the ability of educational institutions to effectively respond to the academic, social, and developmental needs of adolescent learners. The deliberate attention to teacher quality and instructional delivery, curriculum relevance and workload balance, school facilities and resources, learning environment and peer interaction, as well as student support services and extracurricular opportunities, is vital in ensuring that junior high students experience both academic growth and personal development. A significant contribution of this study is the recognition that, at the junior high level, the interaction between curriculum demands, supportive learning environments, and extracurricular engagement fosters a more profound sense of identity formation, resilience, and academic motivation. The study reinforces and extends theoretical frameworks emphasizing student-centered pedagogy, holistic support systems, and the alignment of curriculum with developmental needs, while offering practical implications for strengthening school policies and instructional practices.

The study concluded that these key dimensions collectively shape the satisfaction of junior high students, demonstrating that targeted efforts in these areas can establish inclusive, future-oriented, and empowering learning environments tailored to the unique challenges and aspirations of adolescent learners.

RECOMMENDATION

The results revealed that the lowest-rated aspects of satisfaction among Junior High students centered on the curriculum and academic workload, classroom learning environment, and specific facilities. To address these, several strategic recommendations are proposed.

First, in terms of the **curriculum and academic workload**, the school may consider conducting regular reviews of subject content to ensure alignment with the interests, abilities, and developmental readiness of adolescent learners. Integrating project-based learning, differentiated instruction, and flexible pacing can help reduce academic strain while maintaining rigor. Teacher training on balancing workload distribution across subjects is also encouraged to promote a more manageable and meaningful learning experience.

Second, regarding the **learning environment and peer interaction**, programs that foster inclusivity, respect, and positive peer relationships should be strengthened. Initiatives such as peer mentoring, classroom guidance sessions, and anti-bullying campaigns can help create a safer and more welcoming climate. Teachers should also be supported in employing classroom management strategies that cultivate cooperation, empathy, and respect among students.

Third, particular attention should be given to the maintenance of school facilities and resources, with a focus on restrooms, classrooms, and other basic amenities, as these directly impact students' comfort and well being. Allocating budgetary support for sanitation, regular monitoring of facilities, and establishing student-led cleanliness campaigns can significantly improve satisfaction in this area.

Overall, addressing these lowest-rated dimensions will not only enhance student satisfaction but also contribute to a more holistic and supportive junior high learning environment. By systematically improving workload balance, peer interactions, and facility conditions, the school strengthens its commitment to fostering both academic success and the personal growth and healthy being of its students.

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